

Research Article

Evaluating Student Interest in Renewable Energy through an AI-Generated Educational Video

Kaliyamah Raman^{1,*}, Eddyzulham Abu Bakar², and Shaiful Bahari Mohamad Norani³

¹ Politeknik Sultan Azlan Shah, 35950 Behrang Stesyen , Perak; kaliyamah@psas.edu.my;

² Politeknik Sultan Azlan Shah, 35950 Behrang Stesyen , Perak; eddyzulham@psas.edu.my;

³ Politeknik Sultan Azlan Shah, 35950 Behrang Stesyen , Perak; shaiful_bahari@psas.edu.my

* Correspondence: kaliyamah@psas.ed.my; 0125281507.

Abstract: *This study explores how an AI-generated educational video, The Magical Journey into the World of Renewable Energy, impacts interest levels in renewable energy among electrical diploma students. Designed for the Power System course at Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic, the video uses visual storytelling and AI-driven animations to present key ideas on solar, wind and hydroelectric power. To gauge changes in interest, 65 students completed pre- and post-video surveys. Quantitative results showed a meaningful rise in interest, with mean scores increasing from 3.1 (pre-video) to 4.2 (post-video), suggesting a strong engagement with the material. Qualitative responses pointed to visual storytelling and animations of renewable energy systems as effective in capturing attention. Students also noted that multilingual subtitles boosted accessibility, especially for those less fluent in English. This research suggests that AI-enhanced educational tools can support traditional teaching by making technical topics more engaging and relatable. With growing interest in renewable energy, students may be more inclined to continue learning and eventually pursue careers in this field. This study adds to the conversation on using innovative methods to deepen engagement in renewable energy education.*

Keywords: *AI-generated educational video; Renewable energy; Student engagement.*

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy plays a vital role in combating global environmental issues and it is essential to foster a deep understanding of its concepts among future professionals. However, topics such as solar, wind and hydroelectric energy often fail to engage students due to their complex nature and the limitations of traditional teaching methods. This disconnect between the significance of renewable energy and students' interest levels presents a challenge for educators.

The use of AI-generated educational content has emerged as an innovative way to address this challenge. By incorporating AI technologies, educators can create more engaging and interactive learning experiences. This study evaluates the effectiveness of an AI-generated video in increasing student interest in renewable energy, focusing on students enrolled in the Power System course at Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic. The video, "The Magical Journey into the World of Renewable Energy," uses visual storytelling, multilingual subtitles and interactive elements to present renewable energy concepts in an engaging format. The purpose of this study is to determine whether such AI-driven tools can significantly enhance student interest to explore renewable energy further.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Renewable energy education has become a priority in technical education curricula worldwide, given the growing need for sustainable energy solutions (Twidell & Weir, 2020). However, traditional instructional methods often fall short in engaging students, particularly in complex technical subjects (Boyle, 2017). Previous research highlights the need for more innovative approaches to teaching renewable energy concepts.

AI-generated educational videos offer a modern solution, combining visual elements with AI-driven interactive features to enhance engagement. According to Luckin et al. (2016), AI in education can transform passive learning into an active experience, catering to diverse learning styles. Studies have shown that interactive content, such as animations and videos, can significantly improve comprehension and retention of complex topics (Mayer, 2021). However, less is known about how such tools impact students' interest in technical subjects like renewable energy.

This study aims to build on the existing research by focusing specifically on student interest, which is critical for long-term engagement and learning outcomes.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

This quantitative study employed a pre-test and post-test to assess changes in student interest before and after watching the AI-generated video. The video developed using ChatGPT for storyboarding, Canva AI for visuals, Runway AI for animation, and Veed.io for narration, was integrated into the Power System course.

Figure 1: Screenshot of the instructor with students traveling in the bus.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the instructor explaining hydroelectric power.

Figure 3. Screenshot illustrating various renewable energy sources.

3.2. Participants

The participants were 65 electrical diploma students enrolled in the Power System course (DET30053) at Sultan Azlan Shah Polytechnic. These students were selected because the course content aligns with the key concepts of renewable energy covered in the video. Participation in the study was voluntary.

3.3. Instruments

The primary instruments used in this study were pre-test and post-test questionnaires designed to measure students' interest in renewable energy. The surveys included both Likert-scale questions (1-5) to rate their interest in renewable energy before and after watching the video, as well as open-ended questions to capture qualitative feedback on which elements of the video were most engaging.

3.4. Data Collection

Data were collected through Google Forms. Before watching the video, students completed a pre-test questionnaire to assess their initial interest in renewable energy. After watching the video, students completed a post-test questionnaire to measure changes in interest and provide feedback on specific video features (e.g., visual animations, storytelling, and subtitles).

3.5. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, and paired t-tests were conducted to compare pre-test and post-test interest levels. Open-ended responses were analyzed qualitatively to identify common themes regarding the video's most engaging elements.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Change in Student Interest

The analysis revealed a significant increase in students' interest in renewable energy after watching the AI-generated video. The mean interest score increased from 3.1 (pre-video) to 4.2 (post-video), indicating a positive shift in engagement. The paired t-test confirmed that this change was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

4.2. Video Features Impacting Interest

Qualitative analysis of open-ended responses indicated that students were most engaged by the video's visual storytelling and interactive elements. Many students reported that the animations of solar panels, wind turbines and hydroelectric dams helped them better visualize and understand renewable energy systems. The multilingual subtitles also made the content more accessible to non-native English speakers, enhancing overall engagement.

4.3. Student Feedback on Learning

Students overwhelmingly indicated that the video made complex renewable energy concepts easier to understand. They appreciated the clear and consistent narration provided by Veed.io, which made the learning process more engaging. Several students noted that the visual representation of the energy systems helped bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical understanding.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Impact on Student Interest

The results of this study suggest that AI-generated educational videos can significantly increase student interest in renewable energy. The combination of AI-driven storytelling, interactive visuals, and accessible narration contributed to a more engaging learning experience, which, in turn, fostered higher levels of interest. These findings align with previous research indicating that interactive and multimedia content enhances student engagement in technical subjects (Mayer, 2021).

5.2. Implications for Renewable Energy Education

The increase in student interest has important implications for renewable energy education. As students become more engaged with the subject matter, they are more likely to retain information and pursue further studies in the field. By incorporating AI and AR technologies into the curriculum, educators can enhance learning outcomes and better prepare students for careers in renewable energy.

5.3. Limitations

One limitation of this study is its focus on a single cohort of electrical diploma students. Future research should involve a larger and more diverse sample to ensure the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, while this study measured changes in interest, future studies should also investigate the long-term retention of knowledge gained through AI-generated educational videos.

6. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that AI-generated educational videos, like *The Magical Journey into the World of Renewable Energy*, can effectively increase student interest in renewable energy topics. By using AI tools for storyboarding, animation, and narration, the video provided an engaging and accessible learning experience that resonated with students. The positive change in interest suggests that AI-enhanced learning tools have the potential to transform traditional teaching methods, making complex technical subjects more engaging and easier to understand.

Educators should consider integrating AI-generated content into their curriculum to foster greater student interest and improve learning outcomes in renewable energy and other technical subjects.

References

- Adobe Systems Incorporated. (2024). Premiere Pro: Professional video editing software. <https://adobe.com>
- Boyle, G. (2017). *Renewable energy: Power for a sustainable future* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Canva. (2024). AI image generation for creative projects. <https://canva.com>
- ChatGPT. (2024). AI-assisted storyboard generation. <https://openai.com>
- Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. Pearson.
- Mayer, R. E. (2021). *Multimedia learning* (3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- OpenAI. (2024). ChatGPT: A language model for generating educational content. <https://openai.com>
- Twidell, J., & Weir, T. (2020). *Renewable energy resources* (4th ed.). Routledge.
- Veed.io. (2024). Text-to-speech for educational videos. <https://veed.io>